

A study of the validity of one step (75 grams) oral glucose tolerance test as both screening and diagnosis gestational diabetes

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Abstract

This is a hospital based prospective clinical study was done in 250 antenatal women attending the out-patient Department of OBG, Government General Hospital, Kakinada. All antenatal women after 20 weeks of gestation without a prior history of pre-gestational diabetes mellitus were subjected to 75g oral glucose test irrespective of the time of last meal with a 2nd hour threshold of 140mg/dl. Later they were requested to undergo 100g OGTT after a week explaining the guidelines for test procedure and the results were analyzed and followed up. The mean age of study population is 23.3 ± 3.2 years and 59% of GDM cases belong to age group of >25yrs. The incidence of GDM increases with parity and BMI with one or more risk factors. The proportion of GDM cases in the study population was 8.8 and 7.2% with 75g and 100g OGTT respectively. The sensitivity and specificity of 2nd hour 75g OGTT in relation to 100g OGTT was 100 and 98.2%, with a positive and negative predictive value of 81.8 and 100% respectively. Hence the 2nd hour 75g OGTT can be recommended for the diagnosis of GDM. More than 81.8% required treatment with insulin, and only 18.1% pregnant women with GDM were managed with MNT. The incidence of preeclampsia, maternal infections (UTI), postoperative wound complications, macrosomia, preterm births in GDM was 18.1, 22.7, 4.5, 9, 18.1% respectively. Perineal injuries were not observed in this study whereas more than 5% injuries recorded in various studies. The proportion of neonates who developed RDS and perinatal death was 4.5, 4.5% respectively. Treatment and meticulous management during delivery may decrease the incidence of maternal and fetal complications. Increased rates of caesarean section has been

noted in patients with GDM when compared with overall study population in order to avoid complications like shoulder dystocia, birth trauma etc. But GDM per se is not an indication for C section.

Keywords: Oral glucose tolerance test – Diabetes mellitus - Diagnosis

Introduction

Gestational diabetes (GD) is defined as the glucose intolerance mostly detected during pregnancy which ranged from asymptomatic to moderate and severe hyperglycemia (1). Now a days, the observation of GD is high in the form of insulin resistance that are mainly due to pregnancy hormones, where inadequate compensation by the pancreatic β -cells (2). As the pathophysiology of GD remains unclear, some defined factors are closely associated like familial clustering, diet, lifestyle maternal age and obesity (3).

Any degree of glucose intolerance with the onset or first recognition during pregnancy is defined as Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) (4). Women with history of GDM are at an increased risk of adverse maternal and perinatal outcome and also at increased risk of future diabetes predominantly Type II including their children and therefore there are two generations at risk (5,6).

Adverse maternal and fetal outcomes can occur in any degree of glucose intolerance during pregnancy. The adverse maternal complications include preeclampsia, polyhydramnios, urinary tract infection, prolonged labour, increased operative intervention and development of diabetes mellitus. Adverse effects in utero and during the neonatal period, include macrosomia, metabolic abnormalities, respiratory distress syndrome, stillbirth and subsequent childhood and adolescent obesity (5,7).

A high prevalence of diabetes mellitus is ethnically found in Indian women; and the relative risk of GDM in Indian women is 11 times more when compared to the Caucasian women, necessitating universal screening for glucose intolerance during pregnancy among them (8). Thus there is a need for a cost-effective universal screening and diagnostic method. In India more than 70% of the population live in rural areas, but the rural settings and facilities for diagnosing diabetes itself is limited.

In this scenario, performing an Oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) as recommended by a few international associations (e.g. American Diabetes Association, National Diabetes Data Group, International Association of Diabetes and Pregnancy Study Groups) to diagnose GDM is not possible as the cost involved is prohibitive to perform three blood test, and the women has to visit the clinic atleast twice. Hence there is a need for a simple and economically feasible test to diagnose GDM. In this context, Diabetes in pregnancy study group India (DIPSI) procedure of estimating plasma glucose from one blood sample is cost effective; and hence is a preferred method and can serve both as one a step screening and also as a diagnostic procedure.

Recent trials on second generation oral hypoglycemic agents like Glyburide and metformin have suggested the potential of their use in pregnancy. Metformin crosses the placenta but a large number of observational studies on metformin use in early pregnancy have found no teratogenic effect and can be used as alternative to insulin. Glyburide sulphonylurea which acts by closing K^+ channels in cell membranes of pancreatic beta cells, causing Ca^{2+} influx and secretion of insulin from storage granules and decreases insulin resistance. Acarbose reduce intestinal carbohydrate absorption by inhibiting the cleavage of disaccharides and oligosaccharides to monosaccharides in the small intestine and reduces postprandial hyperglycemia, due to less than 2% absorption in the maternal circulation, these agents may have potential benefits in pregnancy. Thus this study aimed to validate the one step 75gms of OGTT as both screening and diagnostic tool for GDM and to determine the maternal and fetal outcome in diabetes complicated pregnancy.

Materials and Methods

This is a hospital based prospective study conducted among antenatal women attending the outpatient department after 20 weeks of gestation of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department, Government General Hospital, Kakinada. There were a total of 250 pregnant women who were randomly picked up for the period of 20 months. Convenient sample of 250 pregnant women who were satisfying the inclusion criteria underwent newer one step 2nd hour 75 gms of oral glucose tolerance test as well as the standard procedure of 100 gms of OGTT after 3 days.

Pregnant women attending the antenatal clinic after 20 weeks (24 to 28 Weeks) of gestation irrespective of maternal age, gravidity and presence and absence of risk factors for

gestational diabetes mellitus were included in the study. Known diabetic patients before pregnancy (pre-gestational diabetes), patients detected as overt diabetes in first trimester or before 20 weeks and patients with history of usage of drugs that effect glucose metabolism like corticosteroids were excluded in the study.

All antenatal women who have come for checkup after 20 weeks of gestation and met the inclusion criteria were interviewed their family history, previous health status and obstetric outcome. Their height, weight, BMI, blood pressure were recorded. Each pregnant women was given 75gms of glucose dissolved in 300ml of water irrespective of the time of the last meal and two hour venous blood sample were collected to know their plasma glucose levels after taking informed consent.

They were requested to come after 3 days with an overnight fasting of 8 hrs for 100 gms of OGTT. Venous samples were drawn in fasting 1 hour, 2 hours, 3 hours. The results were analyzed taking into consideration 2 hour plasma glucose value of 75gms of OGTT with a cutoff of 140mg/dl of DIPSI criteria and comparing with 100gms of OGTT of Carpenter-Coustan criteria. The pregnant women who were diagnosed as GDM were treated with medical nutrition therapy or insulin and were followed up and the maternal and fetal outcome studied.

Results

The mean age of the study population is 23.3 + 3.2 years and the maximum of 66.8% patients were from 20 to 25 years. Out of 250, 64.8, 20.8 and 14.4% were primigravida, gravida 2, and gravida 3 and above respectively. Only 15 patients were obese (BMI of more than 30 which acts as a risk factor for GDM). While analyzing the risk factors in detail, the previous history of diabetes mellitus (8%), GDM (2.4%), abortions (9.2%), IUD (3.6%), anomalous baby (1.2%). While doing the routine examinations, 7.2 and 6% presented with glycosuria and polyhydramnis respectively. The detailed demographic and basic clinical informations about the study population are tabulated (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic and basal clinical data related to study population

Characteristics	N=250	Association with GDM (n=22)
<i>Age groups (in years)</i>		
<20	31 (12.4)	2 (9.1)
21 – 25	167 (66.8)	7 (31.8)
26 – 30	40 (16)	11 (50)

>30	12 (4.8)	2 (9.1)
Parity		
Primi	162 (64.8)	6 (27.3)
Gravida 2	52 (20.8)	10 (45.5)
Gravida 3	29 (11.6)	5 (22.7)
Gravida 4	7 (2.8)	1 (4.5)
Body mass index (BMI)		
18.5 – 24.9	147 (58.8)	5 (22.7)
25 – 29.9	88 (35.2)	13 (59.1)
>30	15 (6)	4 (18.2)
Risk factors		
Family history of DM	20 (8)	4 (18.2)
History of abortion	9 (3.6)	2 (9.1)
History of abortions	14 (5.6)	3 (13.6)
History of GDM	6 (2.4)	1 (4.5)
History of LGA	12 (4.8)	2 (9.1)
Obesity	15 (6)	4 (18.2)
IUD	9 (3.6)	4 (18.2)
Previous anomalous baby	3 (1.2)	0
Glysuria	18 (7.2)	5 (22.7)
Polyhydromnis	15 (6)	3 (13.6)

[LGA - Large for Gestational age; IUD; Intrauterine device; DM – Diabetes mellitus; GDM – Gestational diabetes mellitus] [Figures in parenthesis denoted percentages]

Out of 250, 22 (8.8%) were diagnosed as positive for GDM with a threshold 2nd hour plasma glucose value of 140mg/dl. 4 (1.6%) were in the range of gestational glucose intolerance i.e.; 121-139mg/dl and were followed up advising dietary restriction and exercises. Remaining population were in the range of normoglycemia. The detailed description of 2 hours plasma glucose of 75 grams OGTT was impregnated in table 2. All the study population were further subjected to 100g OGTT after 3 days and the results were compared thereby 18 out of 22 GDM who were also positive for single step 2nd hour 75g OGTT with a cutoff value of 140mg/dL (Table 3).

Table 2: Test results of 2nd hour plasma glucose of 75g OGTT

2 hours plasma glucose of 75 grams OGTT	Number of subjects (n=250)	Inference
<120mg/dL	224 (89.6)	Normal
121-139	4 (1.6)	Gestational glucose tolerance (GGT)
>140mg/dL	22 (8.8)	Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM)

[Figures in parenthesis denoted percentages]

Table 3: Comparison of study results with 100g OGTT

Gestational diabetes mellitus	2 nd hour 75g of OGTT	100g of OGTT
Positive	22 (8.8)	18 (7.2)
Negative	228 (91.2)	232 (92.8)

[Figures in parenthesis denoted percentages]

In this study, the sensitivity of single step 2nd hour 75g OGTT in relation to 100g OGTT is 100% whereas specificity is 98.2%. Hence it signifies that single step 2nd hour plasma glucose with 75g OGTT with a cutoff value of 140mg/dl can be used as an alternative to 100g OGTT in diagnosing GDM.

Among the GDM patients, seven (31.8%) were recorded as full term normal delivery (FTND) and 4.5% underwent instrumental delivery by forceps. Maximum (63.6%) underwent lower section caesarean section (LSCS) indicating increase incidence of operative delivery. Though there is increased incidence of operative delivery, GDM as one of the major risk factor in pregnancy, but in this study it is not an indication for caesarean section, where post-operative pregnancy was observed among seven LSCS cases and six of them had big baby with CPD (Table 4).

Table 4: Mode of delivery among GDM patients

Mode of Delivery	Number of GDM cases (n=22)
Full term normal delivery	7 (31.8)
Instrumental delivery (forceps)	1 (4.5)
Intrauterine devices (IUD)	3 (13.6)
Pre term delivery	5 (22.7)
Lower segment caesarean section (LSCS)	14 (63.6)

[Figures in parenthesis denoted percentages]

Out of 22 cases diagnosed as GDM, 9 cases were initially managed with calorie restriction and exercise and followed up. Of these 5 cases have further elevated plasma glucose value who were later given insulin. Hence 81.8% (n=18) of cases managed with insulin and others managed with calorie restriction and exercise. GDM is associated with various maternal complications during pregnancy. In this study, there is 18.1% incidence of preeclampsia in pregnant women with GDM, whereas the overall incidence of preeclampsia in study population is found to be 7.2%.

There shows increased incidence of recurrent urinary tract infections than in normal study population. It shows 22.7% incidence of UTI in GDM patients, whereas only 12% incidence in

the overall study population. In study population the proportion of macrosomic babies with birth weight more than 4kgs found to be 4.8%. In cases diagnosed with GDM the average birth weight is found to be in the range of 3 to 3.7kg. Out of this 9% babies found to be macrosomic with birth weight of more than 4kg. The detailed description of maternal complications and fetal outcomes were depicted in table 5.

Table 5: Maternal complications and fetal outcomes

Category	Study population (n=250)	GDM cases (n=22)
Maternal complications		
Preeclampsia	18 (7.2)	4 (18.2)
Maternal infections (UTI)	30 (12)	5 (22.7)
Perineal injuries	6 (2.4)	0
Postoperative wound complications	7 (2.8)	1 (4.5)
Fetal outcomes		
Macrosomia	12 (4.8)	2 (9.1)
Preterm	10 (4)	4 (18.2)
Hyperbilirubinemia	20 (8)	2 (9.1)
RDS	6 (2.4)	1 (4.5)
IUD	3 (1.2)	1 (4.5)
Anamalous baby	1(0.4)	0
Perinatal death – IUD	3 (1.2)	1 (4.5)
Perinatal death – still birth	1 (0.4)	0

[Figures in parenthesis denoted percentages]

Discussion

The history of GDM are at increased risk of future diabetes. Children who are born to mothers with uncontrolled diabetes (pre-gestational or gestational) have four to eight times more likely to develop diabetes in later life when compared to their siblings born to the same parents in a non-GDM pregnancy (9,10,11).

It has been documented that increasing trends of GDM was observed in different states of INDIA. The prevalence of GDM in our study was 8.8% and it is compared to 6% (10); 6.3% (12); 6.6% (13) and 6.7% (14). The GDM prevalence was differed across the different regions of INDIA (15). The highest was found in North region (average of 16.1% and range from 9.9 to 22.7) (16) followed by South India (average of 12.6% and range from 7.8 to 17.8) (17). West, Central and Eastern regions have low prevalence with average and range of 7% (3.3 to 11.2) (18), 12% (4.3 to 21.1) (19) and 11.5% (5.3 to 18.4) (20) respectively.

A meta-analysis revealed the mean age of pregnant women comparatively in two range of years (2015 to 16 and 2019 to 21) was 24.61 and 24.85 years respectively (1,21) and in this study, the mean age was observed as 26.42.

While determining the parity and GDM, 45.5% were in Gravi 2. Literature revealed that the incidence of GDM increased steadily as parity increased from 3.5% in nulliparous women to 14.6% in women with parity ≥ 4 (22). A previous study from Iran reported progressively increasing rates of GDM with increasing parity (23) although another study from Oman did not find a statistically significant association of parity with GDM (24). Multiparous women were eight times more likely to have GDM than nulliparous women (25,26).

The mean BMI in this study 27.3 where this high BMI in pregnancy have its adverse effect on glucose metabolism, and observable maternal and fetal effects notified. There are numerous factors that influencing in pregnancy and its effect on BMI. In common, Asian women are more obese than white may due to the differences in the distribution of body fat across ethnicities south Asian women have greater levels of visceral abdominal fat, an important determinant of insulin resistance. Pre-pregnancy BMI play very important role on insulin resistance in pregnancy (27).

Overall, in this study, the level prevalence of GDM was observed due to the advancement in their life style pattern and the same was recorded in previous study also (28). While analyzing the factors influencing the development of GDM, glysuria, family history, obesity and IUD found top; where other studies revealed advanced age, family history of diabetes, gestational hypertension, history of abortions, macrosomia, placenta previa, polyhydramnios and pre-eclampsia are be the risk factors associated with GDM (29).

The insulin can be detected in fetal pancreas within 9 weeks after conception. The main and important perception is to screen GDM in the first trimester as the fetal β cells that recognizes and responds to maternal hyperglycaemia. The tests may be repeated at 24 to 28 weeks of gestation if the primary test result is negative. This time gap has to be chosen because insulin resistance increases as third trimester progresses and early testing may miss some patients who later develop carbohydrate intolerance (10,30,31).

The induction of the labor risks is the main problem which have to deal with planning of delivery modes those who are with DM and usually ends with caesarean. Among them, the maternal obesity raise the risk of cesarean, along with that the infant respiratory distress

syndrome was observed before 39 weeks due to mothers with DM and also with poor glycemic control (32,33).

In general, Gestational hypertension (GH), preeclampsia, perineal infections and HELLP (hemolysis, elevated liver enzyme levels and low platelet levels) syndrome are the common complications observed among diabetic patients and also considering as the major confounding factors in maternal and fetal outcomes. From our study it emerged that there were 30 (12%) and 18 (7.2%) cases of maternal infections and preeclampsia, with 5 and 4 patients affected by the GDM group respectively.

According to the fetal outcomes to be concerned, the evaluation of total intrauterine fetal growth pathologies including fetal hyperbilirubinemia (8%), macrosomia (4.8%) and preterm (4%); out of that, 2, 2 and 4 cases from GDM patients respectively. Comparatively, fetal growth disorders including intrauterine growth retardation (IUGR), small for gestational age (SGA), fetal macrosomia were detected in considerable numbers (34,35,36). The percentage of neonatal jaundice of diabetic mothers ranged from 11 to 29%. In this study revealed a lower incidence compared to these data (8%) (36,37,38).

Conclusion

By this study, the epidemiological perspective of Indian regional area was studied. Our conclusion stated that there was “a very strong correlation between gestational diabetes and hypertension and preeclampsia”. As more sample size required for generalization, further studies with larger sample size and multiple institutions needed to draw definitive conclusions. In order to reduce and curtail the pregnancy related complications and neonatal adverse events, screening of the mothers for gestational diabetes and its related risk factors, even prior to conception also grateful to avoid the inception of GDM in non-diabetic patients by teaching them to modify risk factors like body weight, sedentary lifestyle and nutrition). The multi-expert opinions and sensitization are to be intensified thereby the pregnancy planning and during all visits is successful.

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